

Code Book - Codes

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This document is a supplementary material of the paper "Analyzing the BizDev Interface in an Enterprise Context: A Case of Developers Acting in Business" by Caique G. Moreira, Breno B. N. de França, and Tayana U. Conte. Here, we provide the part of our codebook that contains the Codes.

ID	Categories	Type	Code	Groundedness	Density	Quotes
cod1	cat1; cat4; cat16	Practice	Leadership constantly sharing business results	5	3	- "And then the coordinators give us a little bit of what's happening in their routine, and some strategic decisions" (P15) - "It happens every two weeks, when we have the meeting with CompanyP's CEO." (P15)
cod2	cat1; cat16	Meeting	Monthly Alignment meeting for presenting company's results	3	2	And from the monthly results meetings (...), we can get more details about what's happening with the business and the product (P15)
cod3	cat1; cat14; cat24; cat26	Conflict	Technology team making business decisions/ acting isolatedly and impacting negatively work of other teams/areas	5	4	- "Because sometimes it's something that I see happening, so the team that knows how to do it, goes, makes a new feature and puts it in. Regardless of the business rule we're following" (P7)
cod4	cat1; cat23; cat26; cat27	Conflict	Business leader and Development leader taking isolated decisions, without aligning other people	8	4	- "They didn't involve people, everything was in their heads, both the Mobile Dev Leader and the Former Product Manager" (P14) - "But yeah, for building features, they talked to each other and no one knew about it" (P14)
cod5	cat1; cat26	Conflict	Employees working isolatedly, without proper alignment with necessary areas	7	2	- "So working in group takes time, and it demands several changes in day-to-day practices. (...) So I think that, combined with the sense of ownership, it promotes people to act more in restricted forums." (P8)
cod6	cat1	Conflict	Technology team bringing too much criticism to Designers' work	2	1	- "So there could be some discomfort with more people meddling in the solution and saying: 'Oh, I think the screen should be here or there', okay, that sometimes annoys the designer a bit." (P8)
cod7	cat1; cat26	Culture	Strong sense of ownership by technology people	4	2	- "I think so, one of the (company) values that I like the most, which I would say is the first commandment, is the sense of ownership, because from the moment you own something, and you care about that something, you will want to do everything to make it work, so that everything goes well" (P10)
cod8	cat1; cat2; cat22	Knowledge	Developer with high knowledge over customer preferences and behavior	11	3	- "Our clients today, we make a product to be used by the child. But our biggest barrier is how to communicate with the parents." (P5) - "So we said, 'okay, how do we translate this recurrence?' We realized that the best way to translate recurrence for a child is to make them take care of something." (P9) - "The idea is probably to evolve FeatureT with some other things. Today, we know that its life cycle is short. Like, the interaction is short. In a minute, you do everything you need to do on FeatureT." (P4)
cod9	cat1; cat2	Culture	Strong customer focus (Company Value) by technology people	7	2	- "Wanting the best, the best possible experience that the user can have. So that ends up pushing the feature in a direction where the result is better. Even before I had this closer contact with our direct customer." (P5) - "I even tested a tool called UserTesting. You can upload a test of your application there and pay for random users to test it and answer your questions. I used that tool a few times." (P5)
cod10	cat1	Culture	Leadership encouraging sense of ownership (Company Value)	7	1	I tell them: 'be the agent of change'. If you see the problem and notice that nobody is addressing it, take action and solve the problem! Don't just point out the problem. (P5)

cod11	cat1	Culture	Company's values with strong presence on employees routine	5	1	- "Yes. The value here, at least at CompanyP, is very intense, very strong. We truly believe that everyone who works here must have CompanyP's values, and they must be present in CompanyP' day-to-day operations." (P5)
cod12	cat1; cat13; cat26	Culture	Sense of ownership encouraging employees to work isolatedly from other areas	2	3	- "It's not an intentional thing to want to deceive people. It's just that, since we also have the drive to create things here, the entrepreneurship aspect of the company's culture, sometimes we want to do something, we have the drive to create, but we end up forgetting that there are people who have expertise in that area. Who have mastery of that subject and it's good to involve them in it." (P8)
cod13	cat1; cat9	Culture	Company's culture promotes freedom for teams to question and make opinions on other areas	4	2	- "The receptiveness is very good, and I credit that to the culture of CompanyP, in general, all people, especially those in leadership positions, are very open to receiving suggestions, and they also feel comfortable giving their opinion on what we're proposing." (P13)
cod14	cat1; cat26	Culture	Organizational culture empowering employees, making them feel directly responsible for solving company's problem and impacting the business	2	2	- "I think that the Sense of Ownership is the most important thing, the company makes you feel like an owner, empowers you, and shows you that even if you're not in a high position, you can impact and change the company's strategy." (P10)
cod15	cat1; cat2	Culture	Culture encourages that technology people develop a business side, acquire business knowledge	1	2	- "CompanyM as a whole encourages us a lot to develop our business side, our strategic side, the CEO himself/herself always says that we are the ones who make the company, we can't wait for someone else to bring the solution to the problems, and take our next steps" (P10)
cod16	cat1; cat26	Culture	Strong idea of meritocracy: The more effort you take for the company, the higher your rewards will be	5	2	- "Look at the mental trigger you create in people. 'Oh, build me something cool, and if you build something cool, you'll get a 5 in your performance review.' You'll be rewarded, you'll get a raise." (P14)
cod17	cat1; cat22	Culture	Culture demands that developers constantly monitor business indicators	2	2	- "HoldingM and CompanyP push this a lot, we always have this issue of either pulling some kind of data or being involved in some kind of decision" (P9)
cod18	cat1	Culture	Individual Development Plan (IDP) motivating involvement with business	1	1	- "So for a month, I've been looking at App Annie to see how ProductP is performing compared to other competitors, getting a little closer to numbers, revenue, and monthly spending of ProductP. I'm starting to take steps in this direction. It's part of my Individual Development Plan (IDP), and that's why I'm going in this direction." (P5)
cod19	cat2	Knowledge	Developer with knowledge of marketing operations	5	1	- "We stopped to think about it because we were in a downward trend in terms of users. There's also a media issue involved, the team cut back on that." (P1)
cod20	cat2	Perception	Developer with limited knowledge of business	2	1	Q: How do you evaluate your knowledge about business? A: "I would say it's very little", "I wish I had more, I believe I could help more if I knew more" (P6)
cod21	cat2	Perception	Developer believes that having more knowledge of business would bring more responsibilities, as they would be aware of more issues.	2	1	- "No, I don't think the day-to-day would be easier. I think it would be even more complicated, because I would have more awareness of the problems, which I don't have today." (P5)
cod22	cat2	Perception	Having more knowledge about business wouldn't make much of a difference for a developer.	1	1	- "Maybe this extra knowledge wouldn't make a difference in my day-to-day. So I think at the moment I know enough." (P9)

cod23	cat2; cat18	Results	Process reengineering project increased knowledge about the scope/operations of different areas.	5	2	- "I think today (after the reengineering project) people have a slightly better understanding (...), at least about it to the Design role, (...) how important the Design perspective was on that, right?" (P2) - "(talking about a result of the reengineering project) People exchanging ideas, in this communication, being concerned beyond their own work" (P8)
cod24	cat2; cat22	Tool	Use of AppAnnie to obtain indicators of competing products	2	2	- "We have a tool called App Annie, which allows us to extract various data on the usage of competitor apps, both monetization and MAU (Monthly Active Users)" (P5)
cod25	cat2	Practice	Employees testing the products produced by the company.	2	1	- "I have a two and a half year old daughter, and I've also had a goddaughter at that age, who is now six. I can see a user up close, working with one of our clients using our product. That helps a lot." (P5)
cod26	cat2	Perception	Having more knowledge of business would be positive for developers.	5	1	- (responding to how it would be if they had more knowledge of business) "For example, prioritization of tasks. Because, whether we like it or not, we prioritize within the technology team according to our own vision" (P1)
cod27	cat2	Perception	Technology teams have an easy time understanding concepts of content and product.	2	1	- "but in the end, they can understand with our explanation (about business) easily. Which often does not happen the other way around. (business team understanding technology concept)" (P12)
cod28	cat2	Perception	Developer with good knowledge of business in general.	3	1	- "I think now I consider that I know a lot about the business" (P4) - "Because at the moment I think I have enough (business) knowledge for what I do." (P9)
cod29	cat2; cat4	Perception	Business knowledge coming naturally given the context of the company.	1	2	- "I think it was natural, you know. As the company, it... I think it's natural... If you don't do anything to chase it... you will learn something (about business). Because the company is involved in it" (P9)
cod30	cat2	Perception	Developer with good knowledge of business in the context of their work (team/project).	2	1	- "And then, this way, I feel that my knowledge of the business is at a good level, at a high level. It is at a good or very good level in the part I am working on, and with regard to the rest of the company, it would be at an average or low level." (P15)
cod31	cat2; cat16; cat28	Knowledge	Business team imparting business understanding to the development team.	3	3	- "Sometimes they notice something and bring it to us: 'Hey guys, we noticed that this is happening' or 'We are planning this because we saw it in the data or some market trend'" (P9)
cod32	cat2	Knowledge	Extensive study of the gaming market by a technology team member.	2	1	- "The whole idea of this opportunity came from analyzing the Competitor Product. Seeing how it, which had been in existence for over 10 years, suddenly became a huge success." (P10)
cod33	cat2	Knowledge	Technology members having their own incentive for involvement with business.	6	1	- Q: Do you believe your leader encouraged your interest in business? A: The interest came from myself, from books about entrepreneurship and news about big companies (P6)
cod34	cat2	Knowledge	Technology team member with high knowledge about indicators and outcome metrics of company products.	4	1	- "When this feature was introduced, it had a much longer session duration than the session duration of other features. In fact, if I'm not mistaken, it was greater than the sum of all other accumulated features." (P15)
cod35	cat3; cat10	Relationship	Development coordinator urging for greater involvement of the product team in the developers' day-to-day work.	1	2	- "But the development coordinator wanted my participation. So it was a middle ground, you know. I started to participate more because he was right. I really needed to be closer to the developers' work, live and direct" (P14)
cod36	cat3	Relationship	Lack of action taken by the company to improve the relationship between business and development.	3	1	Q: Did you see any action from CompanyP to improve the BizDev relationship? - "Man, I don't think it was necessary" (P4) - "No" (P1) - "I believe that the action depends on each one individually" (P6)

cod37	cat3; cat17	Communication	Increased alignment and transparency between business and development teams as an opportunity to increase trust between teams.	3	2	Q: How would you try to build that trust? A: "I think the issue of alignment is more about literally talking, I think it's not even about bringing, showing more work, but rather more ideas. So exchanging more ideas, sharing experiences there, for us to build things forward. But building trust is a daily job." (P7)
cod38	cat3; cat5; cat6; cat19	Responsibility	Product Manager responsible for connecting teams from different areas, facilitating communication and ensuring exchange of information between them.	3	4	- "but I have a primary responsibility in the day-to-day to connect these teams around a specific product point that is common among them" (P8)
cod39	cat3	Responsibility	Developer feeling responsible for facilitating the work of the business team.	2	1	- "So I need to take the complexity of Computing, which is our specialty, and leave the complexity of her (business person's) area to her." (P9)
cod40	cat3; cat4; cat6; cat8	Context	Existence of core teams, multidisciplinary squads composed of everyone involved in a particular project.	3	4	- "It's the Product, UX, and development team. Those are the three main areas, you know. They are the core areas." (P14)
cod41	cat3; cat4; cat5; cat6; cat8; cat16; cat18	Meeting	Multidisciplinary daily meetings, involving technology and business teams.	8	7	Q: What is the composition of people in the dailies? A: "Currently, it is more focused on the production groups, which are design, tech, and product." (P2)
cod42	cat3	Relationship	Efforts to bring development and content teams closer together.	1	1	Recently we started some meetings with the mobile dev team, so that we can get a little closer to what we are building there, inside the application (P3).
cod43	cat3	Relationship	Efforts to bring development and support teams closer together.	2	1	- "There's also the support team, which we're trying to get closer to. (...) We're trying to get closer to them because of past issues, and it's to improve communication with the customer and try to avoid problems in the future." (P9)
cod44	cat3	Relationship	Product Analyst making efforts to improve the relationship with technology team.	2	1	I started having lunch with them gradually, trying to create bonds, trying to have lunch and such. (P14)
cod45	cat4	Perception	Technology teams have responsibilities beyond just the technology area.	3	1	Q: What are your responsibilities? A: "Finding new ways of innovation to bring new people to know the app" (P6) "I feel that we also do other things that are not just technology (...) many projects have also been generated from within" (P9)
cod46	cat4	Perception	Development analyst with the perception of having little impact on business decisions.	1	1	- "My impact on the Business team today would be low, because I am more reactive to what is proposed by the business." (P15)
cod47	cat4; cat27	Perception	Business involvement is restricted to higher management positions.	1	2	- "I believe we don't have a business sector, it's always quite dispersed among managers, directors." (P3)
cod48	cat4	Perception	Technology area trying hard to replicate a success case of idea proposal, but failing because the case was an exception.	3	1	I see that much of what the technology team does is trying to replicate what P10 did with ProductV. In another time, in a completely different company than we have now. (P14)
cod49	cat4; cat10; cat26	Context	Company structure incentivizing individual work to quickly prove ideas and launch them.	2	3	- "So the behavior is given by the structure. So if the structure is based on goals focused on areas, (...) you'll do it. And if that continues to be encouraged (...) You'll think like this: "This idea is really good, let's test it in two weeks, quickly, I'll make it and we'll just launch it"." (P8)
cod50	cat4; cat23	Context	Senior leadership encouraging and challenging technology employees to propose new business directions, giving them a vote of confidence to act	2	2	- "I was able to bring up this point to the leadership, and then the leadership took up the challenge, let's put it that way. So they challenged us, set up challenges, and always encouraged us to think this way." (P10)

cod51	cat4; cat8; cat9; cat21; cat23; cat28	Context	Business making the decision to involve technology teams in prioritization discussions and requirements definition	2	6	- "So the Design, Tech, Growth teams and any area involved in ProductP development were invited to suggest possible solutions for us to tackle that problem" (P8)
cod52	cat4; cat18	Perception	Process reengineering project made those involved feel more influential in the final outcome	1	2	- "They feel more like being really part of the process, felt a little more like owners of that, because they effectively can influence that result." (P8)
cod53	cat4; cat5; cat19	Responsibility	Product Manager responsible for ensuring that all necessary areas are involved/aligned for every project	2	3	(about the responsibility of facilitating communication): "The point of communication is to ensure that the information is reaching those who need it, and that the person who is closest to the work is making the decision." (P8)
cod54	cat4	Responsibility	Technology responsible for understanding user preferences, improving the user experience, and maintaining retention/engagement.	5	1	- (Talking about their responsibilities) - "to be able to support and work together with product, solve the main problems of ProductP, which are: to monetize better, to retain users better" (P5) - "We have to maintain ProductP, insert new features. Always trying to maintain quality. Maintain engagement of our users." (P4)
cod55	cat4; cat16	Responsibility	Product team responsible for validating business ideas brought by other teams	3	2	- "So our responsibility in the Follow Up meetings was also to bring critical arguments to the development team to make the idea "WaterProof"." (P14)
cod56	cat4; cat24	Results	Feature proposed by technology becoming a success case for the company	5	2	Q: Did you see any feature proposed by technology? A: "Yes, I have seen it. There is the case of ProductV. Which was proposed by the technology team, right. This was a big case, by the way. Which is always cited" (P15)
cod57	cat4; cat6	Relationship	Good relationship between development and business teams	11	2	- "I believe that we (content team) have a close and transparent relationship with the platform team (backend devs)" (P3) - "Usually, the product team is very open to any idea we (mobile devs) have. So I think it's very collaborative, in this aspect I think it's good" (P4)
cod58	cat5	Communication	Process of increasing BizDev communication frequency	5	1	- "I think it's not just about including more people in communication, but actually we communicated more" (P7) - "So we are already starting to have more meetings to discuss about some issues, so the Product team will have an increased percentage of participation in conversations" (P15)
cod59	cat5; cat8; cat17	Communication	Increasing BizDev communication frequency helped to solve alignment issues.	2	3	- "I think the alignments helped, more frequent and closer meetings." (P7)
cod60	cat5; cat9; cat20	Context	Increase in transparency of BizDev communication democratizing decision-making process.	2	3	- "This question about the process (reengineering project) is much more about democratizing access and providing transparency, which are the principles of the agile methodology, which is communication and transparency. You need to be able to communicate and provide transparency about what is being done, there's no more to it." (P8)
cod61	cat5; cat18	Results	Process reengineering project improving the prioritization process through better alignment between teams	2	2	- "And then (after the reengineering project), I think this issue became much clearer, right? About how the technology team begins to prioritize projects where everyone is aligned." (P12)
cod62	cat5	Perception	Perception that global actions taken by the company will not be impactful enough to enable BizDev knowledge exchange	3	1	Can the company endorse and help with team efforts? I think definitely, and they should. But they are much more involved in the day-to-day, which are a little smaller than revolutionary cross-company actions. (P8)

cod63	cat5; cat20	Results	Process reengineering project centralized information/tasks from different areas into a single tool	7	2	And everyone is currently using Monday, Dev, Product, Content. So it's easier for us to visualize what everyone is doing, at which point, and also how the progress of each task is going. (P2)
cod64	cat5; cat20	Results	Process reengineering project centralized communication between different areas into a common channel	2	2	- "So that was one of the points (of the Project). There were others. Like having a common channel in Slack. So that you don't have such fragmented exchange of information." (P8)
cod65	cat5; cat20	Results	Process reengineering project involved more teams in business discussions	2	2	- "So the Design, Tech, Growth and any area involved in the development of the ProductP app were invited to suggest possible solutions for us to tackle that problem. So it was a moment of openness" (P8)
cod66	cat5; cat18	Results	Process reengineering project increased alignment among different areas	8	2	- "So today they can involve me more" (P2) - "We have the work communicated and shared in Slack channels. We have it documented in Monday. So you have a lot of security points to kind of guarantee that this doesn't happen. You have weekly meetings where we follow up on the delivery. Design and Tech align" (P8)
cod67	cat5; cat19	Context	Hiring a Product Manager as a company approach to try to improve communication and alignment between areas	1	2	Q: Have you seen any action from the company to try to improve BizDev communication? A: "Besides hiring the Product Manager (P8), no. He was the only one that came to address this issue." (P2)
cod68	cat5; cat6; cat9	Responsibility	Product team with the responsibility of acting as a bridge between teams, reducing communication noise between Business and Development and increasing alignment between areas	9	3	- "So these two [Technology and Business] need to talk to understand where to go. There's the Product figure, which is a middle ground figure, between these two areas." (P14)
cod69	cat5	Communication	Developer making an effort to facilitate communication with non-technical people	12	1	- "And then over time I think they themselves developed this perception that they could be using more technical terms and expressions that we couldn't understand." (P12) - "And then I started explaining to her what it (technical detail) was, and then we moved on. And she was able to understand well what was being conveyed. So I usually do that." (P15)
cod70	cat5	Communication	Business team making an effort to facilitate communication with the technology team	3	1	- "Usually in UX, I avoid using very technical terms that I know they won't be familiar with, and I try to explain more about the logic behind the solution I'm creating" (P2)
cod71	cat5	Communication	Development leader assisting team members to improve communication with non-technical people	1	1	Q: Do you think your leader motivated you? (to improve BizDev communication) A: "Something from the leader does help. Especially for this external vision (...) And there's the point of seeing an example. You watch him doing it" (P9)
cod72	cat6	Communication	Squads greatly improved communication between developers and designers.	4	1	- "so it's much easier to work because we can see the creation and adjustments in real-time" (P5)
cod73	cat6	Communication	Good quality of BizDev communication	4	1	- "Today I think it's much better (communication with dev). We've been able to find a more efficient dynamic than before." (P2) - "So, with all of them, I've never had a problem connecting the business requirement with the technological one." (P8)
cod74	cat6	Context	Company taking action to have recurring forums organized by the HR team with a focus on bringing people closer together	1	1	- "I have been feeling in the last few months that the HR team has been focusing on having many events (...) to bring people from different areas together, to actually bring people who, in a group, form cognitive diversity (...), to discuss topics a little outside that spectrum." (P13)

cod75	cat6	Context	Pandemic forcing adaptation/maturity in relation to remote work	3	1	- "I think the fact that we have been working remotely for a long time also helped a lot because I'm from São Paulo, and the Dev team is from Campinas.. And then even before the pandemic, it often happened that they decided things in informal discussions, in that hallway conversation." (P2)
cod76	cat6; cat7	Context	Members of the business team having technical background	4	2	- "It's easy to have someone in product area who came with a technical background. There are several technical people who turned to the product area." (P5)
cod77	cat7	Perception	Content coordinator with the perception of having good knowledge of technology	1	1	- "I think I have a good level of knowledge for the work I do here." (P7)
cod78	cat7	Perception	Business analyst with reasonable/intermediate knowledge of technology	3	1	- "So I understand a little bit about infrastructure, like if you talk about server, network. I have a basic knowledge of that." (P14)
cod79	cat7	Communication	Use of jargon/technical terms not harming BizDev communication	5	1	- "So I started explaining to her what (technical jargon) was, and then we continued. And she was able to understand what was being conveyed." (P15) - "So there was a lot of jargon in Growth. But nothing... I don't think it hindered communication." (P11)
cod80	cat7	Communication	Technology knowledge helping business people in BizDev communication	4	1	- "I had a strong interface with an IT team from more traditional companies, and that ended up facilitating this type of communication and understanding of technical jargon" (P13) - "So, this closer proximity with the tech side ends up facilitating (understanding of BizDev communication)" (P13)
cod81	cat7	Perception	Content analyst believes that more technology knowledge helps to understand the complexity of the demands they create	3	1	- "And sometimes we may not even request a feature because we know it would be a waste of time if we did. Because it wouldn't be a priority or wouldn't be easy to implement," (P12)
cod82	cat7	Knowledge	Technology knowledge allowing business analyst to question estimation given by technology team.	3	1	- "And then I looked at it and said, "why is this going to take a month and a half? A WebView shouldn't take a month and a half. You have other things to do first, right?" (P7)
cod83	cat7	Knowledge	Technology knowledge assisting business teams in their own work	2	1	- "And understanding this (technical operation), they actually started to understand the content contracts, why we have contracts by territory" (P7)
cod84	cat7	Practice	Business team extracting indicators/metrics	3	1	- "So regarding this strategic aspect, regarding metrics that they (marketing team) need to look at, they are already able to extract that" (P15) - "A third part of my responsibility, I believe, was to analyze data", "go talk to BI tea (...), ask them: help me make this query" (P14)
cod85	cat7	Communication	Business team members having domain knowledge of the IT systems facilitates communication between business and development	5	1	- "I think it flows smoothly (communication), also because it's a platform (system) that we are quite familiar with and so are they (dev team)" (P3)
cod86	cat7	Perception	Analysts of the business area should seek knowledge about technology.	3	1	- "And then I take blame on both sides, (...) us from the Content and Branding team (...) who don't have this specific knowledge, to seek this knowledge and start to understand, you know, how technology works, even to have a better foundation when suggesting a project." (P12)
cod87	cat7; cat16	Knowledge	Isolated exchanges of knowledge in which a technology member transmits technology knowledge to a business member.	2	2	- "I helped the branding analyst with some things. He was really interested in some Javascript stuff. Also, Excel. I showed him that he could create custom functions. I was kind of teaching him some Javascript." (P11)
cod88	cat7	Responsibility	Design team responsible for disseminating knowledge about the scope/role of the area.	1	1	- "This is actually a responsibility of UX as well, to disseminate design culture within the company, and make the understanding of design more accessible." (P2)

cod89	cat7	Responsibility	Product analyst responsible for analyzing data/metrics.	2	1	- "A third part of my responsibility, I believe, was to analyze data" (P14)
cod90	cat7	Knowledge	Business analyst frequently reads about business and technology.	1	1	- "I arrive, I like to arrive early, read some news, especially business and technology news." (P3)
cod91	cat7	Knowledge	Business team with knowledge about design	2	1	- "And then, as the Product Manager already had this more consolidated background, he could tell that "No, this here is something that will impact Design, so I'll involve the Designer"" (P2)
cod92	cat7	Knowledge	Business team with knowledge about technical details (e.g. JSON)	3	1	- "I'll give you an example. All this remote configuration part, which is relatively simple for me, understanding a JSON, it's not complex. Not building from scratch, but adjusting what is already done is easy, I can do that easily." (P13)
cod93	cat8	Perception	Developer with perception that time spent on BizDev communication does not impact day-to-day work	1	1	- "There were a few times in which I've spent some more time. I've had some experiences where it took a little longer to explain something, but overall it's never been something that really got in the way of my day-to-day work." (P11)
cod94	cat8; cat16	Meeting	Follow-up meetings involving technology and business teams	2	2	- "And the follow-up meetings, which in Agile you could say are plannings maybe" (P14) - "So we take the person who gave the idea and put them to talk with the Heads (management). The focal points of each of the interested areas" (P14)
cod95	cat8; cat23; cat28	Meeting	Recurring meetings between content team and development coordinator to define strategy	3	3	Every week we have a meeting, me and the mobile development coordinator, to understand how those games work, how we can develop a way to feed content into them. (...) I believe that's the main focus of these weekly meetings. (P3)
cod96	cat8; cat16	Meeting	Frequent meetings between content coordinator and technology teams	1	2	- "Not scheduled, no. Although we have meetings almost every week." (P7)
cod97	cat8	Communication	Frequent communication between design and product teams	3	1	- "who is the Head of Design. He also has several daily alignments with Product, and with our current General Manager." (P2)
cod98	cat8	Communication	Frequent communication between backend development and content teams	1	1	We'll start first with the PlatformB team, which I think is much more...almost daily contact, especially today with the backend development coordinator. (P7)
cod99	cat8	Communication	Frequent communication between development and design teams	6	1	- "Before starting implementing the layout, I always present my idea to him (mobile development coordinator) to see how it can be implemented, (...) we keep talking about details, (...) showing the layouts" (P2)
cod100	cat8	Communication	Frequent communication between development and Marketing/Growth	4	1	- "Yes. There is a closer contact, especially with the Mobile team. (...) To understand if what I am proposing makes sense, to see if we have already done it in the past, and also to see if there is technical feasibility." (P13)
cod101	cat8	Communication	Frequent communication between development and Product	4	1	Q: With which teams do you communicate outside of IT? A: "The main teams were Product, Growth, and Branding" (P11) A: "Product team, motivation: Validate ideas" (P6) A: "Product, support, content as well" (P1)
cod102	cat8	Context	Success case of a feature proposed by technology had close alignment and follow-up with the business team	1	1	- "So I closely followed the business team, not because they necessarily asked me to, but more because I wanted to push this front and create more interesting things in the future." (P10)
cod103	cat9	Communication	Transparency in communication between content team and development team.	1	1	- "I believe that we have a very close and transparent relationship with the backend platform team (...) I think we have good communication over time estimation, deadlines, it gives me some security." (P7)

cod104	cat9	Context	No friction to show progress of feature implementation to business team	1	1	Q: How frequent is the product's feedback cycle? A: "There isn't really a specific moment of 'Oh, now I'm going to show it to the Product Manager.' It's more like, 'Hey, it's looking good' or 'I don't really like it, I'll show it to the Product Manager.' It usually happens during development itself." (P4)
cod105	cat9; cat16; cat23	Requirements	Technology team presenting proposed directions to the Board	4	3	- "Then we put together what we had structured and made a presentation for the Product Director." (P1) - "And then we realized that we can sell this to the Product team more easily. So we put together a presentation. Presented to the Product Director, presented to the Product Manager, presented to the Head of Technology." (P9)
cod106	cat9; cat16; cat23; cat28	Requirements	Business team used to validate ideas coming from development team	4	4	- "Motivation for contact with product: Validating ideas" (P6) - "I have contact with the product analyst to validate if the idea should be implemented in the app at this time. My team comes up with ideas, the development leader tells us to pass them on to the product manager, who checks if the idea has already been implemented, because they are keeping an eye on the market and verifying that we are not going in the wrong direction." (P6)
cod107	cat9	Requirements	Short maximum waiting time for requirement clarification	4	1	- "Sometimes it happens to go a whole day without a response, then I go to Slack, ask, and the person answers me as quickly as possible." (P9)
cod108	cat9; cat21; cat28	Prioritization	Transparency in communication between Development and Content facilitating prioritization activities	1	3	- "And this (transparency in communication with devs) I think is a very good thing, it gives me security. There are features I can wait weeks to be done, but there are features that I cannot. I think the transparency of the workflow processes of each team is the most important thing. If something is blocking my work and I can't do anything else, I now I just need to come with the information: (...) "I can't work without this being resolved"." (P7)
cod109	cat9; cat21; cat23	Requirements	Entire Development team participating in discussions of requirements and prioritization.	2	3	Q: And who participated in the decision of what to cut from the scope? A: "It was the entire team. The entire team (mobile development), who would be involved in some way" (P9) - "I started doing the Roadmap (meetings), it started to improve, and over time I started calling them to the meetings, I called everyone (mobile development team)" (P14)
cod110	cat9; cat16; cat23	Practice	Development team making business inquiries	3	3	"Q: Has anyone ever given suggestions about your scope of work? A: "It happens all the time. It happens a lot and I think that's partly because of our company culture. (...) I think that's very cool, and it's cool because I also have the freedom to ask the same question to other teams" (P3) A: "Yes, but it has happened that they try to change decisions made by the Content team. (...) And they questioned why we hadn't included certain content. (...) And it was something that, in my opinion at least, we shouldn't waste time on, it's already proven, so it doesn't make sense for us to discuss it again" (P7)"
cod111	cat9	Communication	Business team not needing to directly approach the development leader, being able to talk to subordinates	10	1	- "Another way (of receiving feature demands) is when (business) people come directly to me or someone on the team and inform a problem that is happening, or request something that they already know is a well-defined task. And they pass on this demand." (P15)
cod112	cat9; cat25	Communication	Disagreements generating healthy discussions between business and development	5	2	- "So the product analyst tried to find a middle ground that would be good for everyone. So I think that's why there was never anything too conflicting." (P11)

cod113	cat9	Tool	Use of Slack for communication between two physically separated teams.	8	1	- "It's just that, since the support team is in another city, we can't talk in person, so we have a support channel on Slack that's unified for the entire technology team." (P1)
cod114	cat9; cat28	Context	Business team receptive to technology team's ideas	7	2	- "If we disagree or not, we talk about it: 'Dude, I don't think so because of this, this, and this'. And normally they are open to other opinions" (P4) - "Talking to business people we can pass on some of the ideas and gain some tips to later dig into the data and prove that it will really work" (P15)
cod115	cat9; cat16	Requirements	Developer can/should go directly to the business team to clarify requirements	10	2	- "When in doubt about a feature, ask the person who brought it up, communication via Slack and in-person communication" (P6) - "Usually, I prefer to go and talk to everyone in person" (P5) - "So it often happens that the task will have a note saying: Talk with the Product Manager and understanding the problem better" (P4)
cod116	cat9; cat16; cat27	Requirements	Business team goes directly to developer(s) and presents new requirements	7	3	Usually the Product Analyst would come directly to me, when it was something I needed to do, and not something that involved everyone. So she would directly follow up with me. (P11)
cod117	cat9	Communication	Product team easily accessible for communication with development and design team	3	1	- "But especially regarding the Product team, when we are having some problem with communication and need clarification, they are usually very helpful and they provide us with all the context that we need." (P15)
cod118	cat9	Communication	Development team is very available/accessible to Content team.	2	1	- "So I can really see a strong sense of urgency, (...), of always being available to solve these urgent problems and then make themselves available to report what really happened, what correction was made, and how it can impact future actions." (P12)
cod119	cat10; cat12; cat14	Communication	Physical distance between different teams making alignment difficult.	4	3	- "Here we have a particularity which is the distance between offices, (...). There are teams in different offices and this (communication) has to be closer. The closer we got, the more alignments we made, and the less this (communication barriers) happened." (P7)
cod120	cat10; cat12; cat13; cat14	Communication	Having Product team interface conversations hindered BizDev communication.	2	4	- "Sometimes we don't talk directly with marketing and use Product to interface, and then we sometimes end up with problems. Sometimes, maybe just talking directly with Marketing would solve all the problems." (P9)
cod121	cat10	Communication	Business analyst feeling intimidated to ask business questions.	1	1	- "If you say 'I don't agree' it will create a really tense atmosphere, it will be a terrible thing." (P14)
cod122	cat10	Perception	Product team not being able to fulfill role of integrating teams.	1	1	- "I think what was missing for the Product team is: how do we draw a line and sew these people together to take them to the same place. That was missing. But to have that, we needed to know what the objective was." (P14)
cod123	cat10; cat27	Conflict	Business strategy presented by management/directors at a point where it is no longer possible to contest them.	3	2	- "There is a meeting in which the product director announces the decision. (..) I cannot challenge him (..) it's not possible, impractical. So these forums are not for transparency, not like that." (P14)
cod124	cat10	Conflict	Decision-making being defined by politics: those who assert themselves in communication, who have more influence and charisma.	7	1	- "I do believe that CompanyP really needed these processes because prioritization, and decision-making itself are extremely subjective. This is terrible because it leads to this issue of charisma, where the most charismatic person, the one who speaks louder, who positions themselves better, is the one who makes the decision, and that is very bad." (P14)
cod125	cat10	Relationship	Conflicting relationship between Product Analyst and Development Coordinator.	8	1	- "So, my communication with the analysts is infinitely more peaceful than I think it is with the coordinator." (P14)

cod126	cat10	Relationship	Product Analyst feeling like an outsider in the technology team.	2	1	- "and I would distance myself from the development team because I felt like an intruder, I didn't feel like I was needed, I felt like they didn't think my work was relevant" (P14)
cod127	cat10; cat12	Context	Physical separation between development and business teams.	5	2	- "It's not a very smooth communication, especially because they are in another city. Usually it's written communication." (P1)
cod128	cat10; cat12; cat23; cat26; cat27	Context	Decision-making power over the product spread in silos, in different areas.	4	5	- "So the management was scattered in silos. That is, there was much more activity happening within the Tech world, Design world, each area's world" (P8)
cod129	cat10	Context	Product team isolated from technical teams	2	1	- "What I felt when I joined ProductP: The product team was very isolated, very close to the CPO, close to the management perhaps, and the technical team was closer to the Head of Technology, closer to his influence, and making decisions without consulting the product team" (P14)
cod130	cat10	Communication	Niche communication, not involving all areas that should be involved	1	1	In order to not have such a fragmented exchange of information, sometimes the information ends up being niched. For this reason there would be cases when we people would work on something without the rest of the team having visibility of how the progress of that work is going. (P8)
cod131	cat10	Communication	Violent communication as a present issue	6	1	- "I had a lot of difficulty communicating with him properly and in the right way. Non-violent communication was not practiced, and we had many small conflicts." (P14)
cod132	cat10	Perception	Male-dominated technology environment intimidates communication from women business employees	1	1	- "And then, besides that, I bring up a point, which is the issue of the technology environment being a very masculine environment, and that can sometimes cause some discomfort when a woman comes to communicate." (P14)
cod133	cat10; cat14	Perception	Information loss occurs when using Slack for BizDev communication	1	2	- "I don't like to talk on Slack because the information is usually lost there. I prefer to sit with the person and talk (in person)." (P5)
cod134	cat11	Knowledge	Lack of technical knowledge hindering/restricting the work of the business team	3	1	- "She (business person) didn't know how remote configuration (feature) worked, she didn't have visibility that there was a tool for it, and what would be the scope regarding the feature, without asking development team itself. So I think this is a gap, (...) making it accessible for non-technical people to work on perhaps slightly more technical points. I think we could work on that." (P13)
cod135	cat11; cat12; cat14	Communication	Use of jargon/technical terms impairing Biz/Dev communication	6	3	- "I have difficulty communicating with non-technical people. I have to think before speaking, how to contextualize for the person" (P6) - "when he (business person) passed on to us what he was thinking, for him it was very clear, but the other people were kind of confused about what it meant. And then we needed to ask more about it, for him to clarify what those things meant" (P15)
cod136	cat11	Communication	Difficulty in explaining the responsibilities of different technology teams to business personnel who don't understand technical details.	1	1	- "It is easier to explain things for the Product Manager, because he understand the technical aspects. I think it would be more difficult to explain to the Product Analyst. I feel afraid of appearing to be stalling when in reality, I have dependency on an external team." (P6)
cod137	cat11	Communication	Lack of knowledge of technical terms/jargon making business analysts feel intimidated, hindering their ability to discuss with developers	4	1	- "They (developer analysts) are much more technical and can't get out of that box of technical words. For me, this is not so much of a problem in general, but it is for some people on my team, especially. So sometimes they feel cornered to give an answer: 'I think I'm right, I think I understood. But I'm afraid to continue this conversation because I feel like I don't know what I'm talking about.'" (P7)

cod138	cat11; cat12	Communication	Lack of technology knowledge by business people making communication slower	2	2	- "Sometimes I feel a certain difficulty of some people to understand how some technology things work, and then it starts to become..., then you have to sit down like "come here, let's explain". Like technology 101" (P9)
cod139	cat11; cat14	Communication	Use of technical jargon/terms by the technology team introducing noise in the BizDev communication	1	2	- "So many things, many terms, many dynamics, many operations we don't know. And then there ends up being a communication conflict, right? Where one person is talking about a certain thing, as if the other person was equivalent, but they're not. So this generates a communication noise that needs to be aligned" (P12)
cod140	cat11	Communication	Use of technical jargon/terms by business people making BizDev communication slower.	2	1	- "I have the feeling that that when I talk to people from other areas, they use a lot of jargon and I don't understand, reaching a point where I have to stop the other person and ask them to explain what they are saying in a way that I understand" (P15).
cod141	cat11; cat14	Communication	Problems of understanding/comprehension in communication between development and business	7	2	- "Because if the person speaks using too much technical jargon, then the other person fails to understand, and since they only communicate through exchange of messages (...) sometimes the communication get mixed up" (P7) - "Because there were also some recent situations where while we were discussing a feature, the communication was unclear." (P15)
cod142	cat11	Knowledge	Difficulty for business analysts to find technology material that is accessible to non-technical people	1	1	- "I have a bit of difficulty in getting references for this information (...). I think it's very difficult to find content that isn't too technical. That explains the processes without being too technical, to the point that a non-tech person can understand" (P12)
cod143	cat11	Knowledge	The technology team does not systematically spread technical knowledge to other areas of the company in an organized manner	5	1	- "I don't think that happens in general. In fact, I think it's a great opportunity" (P13)
cod144	cat11	Perception	Business analysts with little knowledge about technology	1	1	- "I think I understand very little about technology as a whole. And I absolutely don't understand anything about development" (P3)
cod145	cat11	Context	Business teams lack knowledge about the roles and responsibilities of the design team.	4	1	- "I had some difficulty with the product analyst because she didn't have a background in design, so sometimes she would interfere with things. Of course, it wasn't with bad intentions, but we had some communication difficulties because since she didn't understand, she would take the lead on things without consulting me." (P2)
cod146	cat12; cat14	Communication	Technology teams struggling to communicate without using too many technical terms/jargon	6	2	- "And today, I believe this may be the biggest difficulty we have when we talk (...) there's always some time for us to try to understand what this technical implementation is (...) and it's not normally very clear. So it's a bit more work to do this translation" (P3) - "I also notice that the technology team has very technical things, and for someone from outside, sometimes it's difficult to understand it" (P12)
cod147	cat12; cat14	Communication	BizDev communication problems due to physical separation between departments	4	2	- "It's not a very smooth communication, especially because they are in another city. Usually it's written communication." (P1) - "I felt some difficulties in talking to the technology team, and I thought it could be related to some points. The first is due to the geographical distance, as the whole team is in another city." (P12)
cod148	cat12; cat13	Context	Unavailability of business leader affecting the speed of delivery for development/design team	2	2	- "Because he has very little time available. He's usually in a meeting or something. He's always running with something. It's difficult to talk to him. (...) Maybe it would speed up (deliverables) if we could exchange more ideas with him." (P4)

cod149	cat12; cat13	Communication	Design team's unavailability resulted in development team developing a feature without consulting/aligning with anyone from Design.	1	2	- "So the ProductP was without anyone working on it for a while (...) And during that time, the developers started to think of things because they had to keep feeding the application. And then there was the featureT, which was thought of without involving so much Design (Team)." (P2)
cod150	cat12	Communication	Preference for face-to-face communication in BizDev interface	9	1	- "Usually it's talked about in person." (P1) - "Normally it's spoken. I usually get up and go to the person to talk." (P5) - "What I like to do usually is to go personally talk to the person. If I can't, I always make time for some channel, but it has to be a conversation by audio, not by text." (P5)
cod151	cat12; cat15	Communication	Development analysts feeling intimidated/reluctant to communicate with other teams	3	2	- "Usually, the lower you go in the hierarchy, the less the technology team talks to the other teams. There's a fear of talking, shyness of talking", "I would say it's shyness/difficulty in communication. (...) So the guy prefers to exchange 15 DM messages than to make a call that will take 2 minutes" (P7)
cod152	cat12; cat15	Communication	Business members preferring to talk to development leaders first, rather than development analysts	10	2	- "And then in the end I looked at everything and said: 'Okay, I'm going to talk directly to his leader, to see what happened, to understand and be able to handle it'" (P7) - "As for the app team, I confess that I don't have as much contact with the team itself. I have much more contact with the coordinator. Who is the person I always look for when I need some more specific information" (P12)
cod153	cat12; cat15; cat16	Requirements	Business team passing requirements to the development leader, who then passes them to the team.	8	3	- "Sometimes, the Product Manager talks directly with the Development Coordinator, who creates the Trello board, and then we (the team) get to know about it." (P4)
cod154	cat12	Communication	Business team using jargon/terms from the business area	4	1	- "Because I feel like the business team is much more used to some technical jargon. (...) So sometimes when they bring a demand to us or bring a problem, they already talk in these jargons or using these terms that may not be known to the technical team." (P15)
cod155	cat13	Communication	Little communication between mobile development team and content team	2	1	Because they have total control over the settings now. I no longer have to interface with them. (P9)
cod156	cat13; cat14	Communication	Teams without knowledge of what the other team is doing	4	2	- "But one thing that we don't do much and that maybe we should improve is the communication with the marketing team for example. We have almost no communication with them, zero. We hardly know what they are doing for example" (P9) - "We didn't have a vision of what the other teams were working on. And who are the responsible areas for each project" (P12)
cod157	cat13	Conflict	Lack of communication between technology teams led to feature being announced without being launched	1	1	- "Marketing had created a campaign without talking to the technology team to ask if it was ready, and then we realized "oh no, it's not ready." But they had already sent out an email (to the customers), you know." (P9)
cod158	cat13; cat26	Culture	Idealization of the heroic worker who stands out, solves everything alone, and sacrifices themselves for the company	2	2	- "And that encourages individualized work, encourages the hero feeling: 'I'm the hero, I can save. I can do it alone.' I don't believe in that, I believe in teamwork." (P14)
cod159	cat13	Meeting	Growth Analyst not participating in regular meetings involving technology teams	1	1	- "Within ProductP, I don't have it anymore. There were changes in product management. (...) And along the way we did have regular meetings. But in the last 2 months we haven't had them anymore." (P13)
cod160	cat13	Communication	Little communication between Backend development and Product	2	1	I think the Product team was farther away from us (backend development team) for a while, and maybe closer to the Mobile Development team. (P15)

cod161	cat13	Communication	Developer communicating infrequently with non-technical people	1	1	- "I don't think so, 90% of the time the people we talk to are from technology" (P1)
cod162	cat14; cat26	Communication	Lack of alignment on directions and decisions between business and development teams	9	2	- "Actually, it was funny, because it didn't involve the product team at first" (P9) - "Several times it happened that we were doing something and we discovered that the other team had already done it. This happens quite frequently here. I had plans to do something, and then I found out that the product team had plans to do the same thing" (P9)
cod163	cat14	Communication	Communication noise in the BizDev interface	6	1	- "It doesn't make sense! I talked to the product team, and they also said it doesn't make sense. (..) Then, a week later: 'So, are we launching the feature?' But did you talk to the product team? And the product team said it really doesn't make sense. (..) The next day: 'Can I release the feature now?'" (P7) - "There have been a few times where I passed something to the product analyst, and then in a follow-up, she passed it on a little differently, you know. And then I realized she didn't understand what I had said." (P11)
cod164	cat14	Results	Feature proposed by technology teams did not achieve expected success due to not having involved other areas	6	1	- "It (the feature) could have been better perceived if it had started together with Product (Team). Why? One of the things that Product does is deal with the board. And featureT lacked that political force, to be something worth continuing." (P14)
cod165	cat14; cat24; cat26	Conflict	Development team putting features online without aligning with all necessary business areas	3	3	- "I think it's becoming less frequent, but it still happens (..). So for example, we had that feature, and they (developers) started looking for reasons to remove the feature. And I looked and said, "Why was this feature prioritized in the first place? It doesn't fit with the app's design." (P7)
cod166	cat14	Conflict	Lack of BizDev alignment generating communication noise and confusion about task scope and who should execute it	3	1	- "There were some issues with communication failure on both sides. When aligning a feature, discussing what were the important points (..) the Tech team as a whole understood it differently." (P13)
cod167	cat14; cat24; cat26	Conflict	Development team defining and implementing features that harm other aspects of the business	4	3	- "Because sometimes it's something that I see happening, so the team that knows how to do it, they go, they make a new feature and they launch it on the app. Regardless of the business rule we're following. Regardless of the overall direction we're following. (...) The person went there and tried to solve the problem and put any feature there because they know how to code." (P7)
cod168	cat14	Context	Business teams with a lack of knowledge about the responsibilities and role of the Design team	4	1	- "But... I think this lack of background (on design) also hindered because the person didn't know when we should be involved in the conversation." (P2)
cod169	cat14	Communication	Preference for speaking in person rather than through text to facilitate communication between technical and non-technical personnel	5	1	- "What I usually like to do is to personally talk to the person. If I can't, I always make time for some channel, but that has audio conversation, not text." (P5)
cod170	cat14; cat27	Requirements	Requirements defined without a discussion forum, involving only teams closer to execution and failing to involve areas that would be affected	1	2	- "because sometimes the topic, that detail is a little more complex, and then the person prefers to have a conversation to discuss it rather than write a long message." (P15)
cod171	cat15	Communication	Development leaders with better communication skills with business teams	3	1	- "I see that leaders are able to do this more (abstract technical terms in communication)." (P12)

cod172	cat15	Communication	Experience improving BizDev communication	3	1	- "So you have to deal with different people, and then you inevitably will be put in situations that require a little bit of finesse. So you'll have to expose yourself in situations. You'll get tangled up, you'll toughen up, and you'll learn. And that's where a bit of professional experience and seniority comes in." (P9)
cod173	cat15	Communication	Lack of social skills hindering BizDev communication	3	1	Q: Do you think hierarchy influences the quality of communication? "So I don't think it's hierarchy. I think it's something related to shyness, or difficulty in communication.." (P7)
cod174	cat15	Communication	Different development teams having varying ease of communication with business teams	3	1	- "It depends on the team. With the backend development, it happens fewer times"
cod175	cat15	Communication	Different levels of social and BizDev communication skills among technology team members	2	1	Q: Do you think that other members of your team are also able to translate technical terms? A: "No, I think it depends on different levels. It also depends on social skills, the ability to communicate well. So it varies from person to person." (P9)"
cod176	cat16	Communication	Business team reaching out to development/design for historical information	2	1	- "So since I'm one of the few people who have been at ProductP for a longer time (...), they also talk to me a lot to pull up history, and we can kind of decide from there, you know." (P2)
cod177	cat16	Communication	Business team communicating with technology team to verify technical feasibility of a solution	3	1	- "And also thinking about the difficulty of implementing new features. Whenever we have an idea (...) we talk to the technology team (...) to understand how feasible it is, how much time it would require." (P12)
cod178	cat16	Requirements	Support team creating demands for the Development team.	2	1	- "And we also have a lot of contact with the support team, who have a common channel on Slack where sometimes demands arise from there." (P1)
cod179	cat16; cat23; cat28	Requirements	Technology team is involved in initial discussions of solution building	7	3	- "And the idea is that we discuss this not necessarily when the solution is relatively ready. We, even during the analysis, ping the stakeholders and specialists in this so that they can give a little feedback and put their finger on that solution that we are developing." (P13)
cod180	cat16; cat18; cat23; cat28	Requirements	Ideation process around goals, involving both technology and business teams	1	4	- "we put an ideation process around objectives. So, in summary, what we did was: declare an objective or result to be achieved within a period of time (...) We presented it to all teams that worked on the app and collected feedback (...) So, the Design, Tech, Growth teams and any area involved in the development of ProductP were invited to suggest possible solutions (...) it was a moment of openness, we collected the ideas that the areas brought. We prioritized them according to the information we had." (P8)
cod181	cat16; cat23; cat28	Requirements	Business and development working together to define strategy and requirements.	9	3	- "And then I went to the Product Manager: 'we're selling very little'. How can we solve this? Then we started discussing ways to solve it. (...) We started talking to find solutions. He came up with an idea, (...) and then we worked to try to build this feature." (P9)
cod182	cat16; cat28	Requirements	Alignment with Product team to remove features from a planned delivery	1	2	- "If they (Product) can add in some way, for example, "which feature to remove", "what can I reduce or not", then certainly we have to involve the entire group, we never make that decision alone, because it always has to be the whole team." (P5)
cod183	cat16	Requirements	Marketing/Growth team requesting features from the technology team	4	1	- "Marketing. Many times it's marketing. (...) Adding support for a tool they use. Or adding events they'll use to segment the base" (P4)
cod184	cat16; cat18	Meeting	Retrospective meeting involving technology and business teams	2	2	- "So Daily and Retrospective are two meetings that are part of the agile cycle and are attended by those who are shipping the product." (P14)

cod185	cat16; cat28	Meeting	Brainstorming meeting open to people from different areas.	7	2	- "This was an idea that came from technology. The product team raised (the problem), so in a brainstorming session that was held with everyone, the feature was born. It was an idea from the technology team, but it came from a brainstorming session with everyone. And then it was implemented and is now live." (P5)
cod186	cat16; cat18	Meeting	Roadmap meeting involving technology and business teams, leaders, and analysts	7	2	- "We have a weekly RoadMap meeting, which is a presentation of the status of the main projects happening in the Product for any StakeHolder. That means any area interested in it can participate, any person from the company, so it's an open round of presentations, on the main points of the App." (P8)
cod187	cat16	Prioritization	Developer clarifying feature priority with Product team	1	1	- "whoever added the card, sets the priority there, talks to the product team, and checks what they are expecting" (P4)
cod188	cat16; cat21; cat22; cat28	Prioritization	Development team justifying to other areas the importance of their direction proposals	6	4	- "This project was quite large and needed approval from the business team before it could be developed. So we raised several metrics related to the product we already had and what could be done to validate it by the business team." (P15)
cod189	cat16; cat21; cat28	Prioritization	Discussion about priority between development and business teams	12	3	- "And then we discussed, and saw if there was anything to add to the backlog, and then she (product analyst) would write down the requirements with us."
cod190	cat16	Responsibility	Business team responsible for providing guidance and inputs that will guide the work of the technology team.	4	1	- "But the business teams are the ones who pave the way." (P14) - "So your business team is responsible for bringing you inputs, so you can release your product and understand what's going on. So that's their responsibility." (P14)
cod191	cat16; cat21	Responsibility	Development analyst responsible for defining prioritization with the business team	1	2	- "So our responsibility was first to (...) somewhat decide with the Dev team what the responsibility and priority was. (...) We had meetings with the Product team, where we defined the priority." (P11)
cod192	cat16	Communication	Clarification of requirements as the main reason for BizDev communication	2	1	- "It was usually when I needed to talk to someone from Product to discuss a feature, a behavior, or even a business rule that we already had. It was more to get clarification. So it was as needed, it was on-demand." (P15)
cod193	cat16	Communication	Discussions about bugs as the main reason for BizDev communication	2	1	- "Almost daily contact, especially nowadays, with the Backend Coordinator. It's a very recurrent contact, mostly focused on the bugs we have." (P12)
cod194	cat16	Communication	Delivery problems reported to the Product team	2	1	- "But we would have to involve Product probably. Say that we couldn't (...) and we need one more week. (...) So we would probably involve them and let them know." (P9)
cod195	cat17	Perception	Mentorship as a possibility for people in technology to learn more about how to sell/conduct their business proposals/directions.	1	1	Q: "Do you think there is any action that the company could take to facilitate people's knowledge and enable them to better sell their proposals?" A: "I think this is a very interesting work to be developed in mentoring" (P10)
cod196	cat17	Communication	Perception that there are no major points to be improved in BizDev communication	2	1	Q: Do you see any points that could be improved in communication with IT? A: "I think that in communication itself, maybe not. There were some points of failure, (...) I don't know if it was really a problem with communication itself. Or if it was that I didn't know how to solve it. But.. I would say no, I would say no." (P11)
cod197	cat17	Communication	People in technology making better synthesis of information, abstracting technical details, as an opportunity for improvement in BizDev communication	1	1	- "And on the Tech side, I think it's the continuous improvement of... synthesizing information. So it's very common for us to get caught up in the technical details because the devs get excited about them." (P13)

cod198	cat17	Communication	Translation of Goals/KPIs into more applicable concepts in day-to-day work as an opportunity for improvement in BizDev communication	5	1	- "We discuss a lot about financial results, which is great, the transparency of the results, but it's not very useful in our day-to-day to guide anything. (...) There's a gap between this information and the day-to-day of delivering a feature." (P8)
cod199	cat17	Communication	Diversifying forms of communication, such as documenting conversations and decisions, as an opportunity for improvement in BizDev communication	4	1	- "Perhaps documenting the conversation and reinforcing it in different ways would be a good opportunity for improvement." (P13)
cod200	cat17	Communication	Management bringing more business context and motivation for objectives as an opportunity for improvement in BizDev communication	2	1	- "So people in management, especially those in product, who necessarily always bridge Business with design, with tech, with all these areas to direct the product, need to make some active effort to transmit this knowledge" (P8)
cod201	cat17	Communication	Multidisciplinary squads as an opportunity to improve alignment between Business and Development teams	1	1	- "Maybe gather everyone who participates in solving a problem to align as a mini team. So create these squads for each problem, and if we can bring all these people together and make more alignments with all of them, then these communication problems can be reduced" (P15)
cod202	cat17	Communication	Increasing the frequency of BizDev communication as an opportunity to improve communication	4	1	- "Maybe, especially on the Business side, we should err on the side of over-communication, and on the other side too. We should err on the side of over-communication, especially in this context of the pandemic and social isolation." (P13)
cod203	cat17; cat27	Communication	Broader BizDev alignment, not involving only leaders, as an opportunity to improve BizDev communication	2	2	- "And I think that if we had some alignment where everyone participated (...) it could help a lot in aligning between teams. I think that in the long run, this would contribute a lot to improving communication relationships between teams." (P12)
cod204	cat18	Perception	BU restructuring bringing setbacks in relation to gains brought by the process reengineering project.	5	1	- "But also, since a lot of new people arrived who weren't there when he (Product Manager) implemented this process, that's why I'm afraid that we might regress in this sense because these people weren't there, and I don't know if they will have an understanding of how this can affect our day-to-day dynamics, given that they are new." (P2)
cod205	cat18	Perception	Process reengineering project enabled all areas to genuinely participate in all stages of the project	1	1	- "So, this makes her spontaneously have a greater concern for the quality of this delivery and goes beyond her work. So, I think the process that we started to implement promotes this." (P8)
cod206	cat18	Perception	Process reengineering project brought more assertiveness in deliveries	1	1	- "There's no way, I'm adding things to the system, it's impossible for it to get faster. But I'm adding assertiveness. So if I find the right balance, and I succeed in doing that, I'll generate more results for the company in a general way." (P8)
cod207	cat18	Perception	Reengineering project helps to avoid charisma and political influence from impacting decision-making as much	1	1	- "But I noticed that the decision-making process in product (area), that is, the product strategy, sometimes depended on how well you communicated and who you were inside. So the work that the Product Manager does in bringing process is extremely important." (P14)
cod208	cat18	Perception	Process reengineering project exposed communication issues	2	1	- "Some pains became clearer, more exposed. Like, how disconnected some of our actions are from the Branding or UA areas, for example. So, for better or for worse, when you implement such a practice, you also reveal what your main pains are, they become more transparent." (P8)
cod209	cat18	Results	Process reengineering project did not achieve expected KPIs after first development cycle	1	1	even though we did not achieve the proposed results, the KPIs that we set as success criteria, and it is also very difficult to achieve it in the first round. (P8)

cod210	cat18	Results	New development cycle was able to deliver most of the planned features	1	1	- "For a first implementation of something like OKR, it was very good. Because we had a delivery rate of almost 80% of the features we committed to. We were also able to deal with several technical debts that appeared in the app during this period." (P8)
cod211	cat18	Results	Process reengineering project received good feedback from the involved areas after the end of the first cycle	1	1	- "We also collected feedback from the team about what they thought of this first phase, what was missing, and overall the feedback was good. People liked being involved and felt more clarity about their activities." (P8)
cod212	cat18	Results	Process reengineering project better organized the creation/proposition of new projects by different areas.	4	1	I find this process interesting because it allows you to think, talk about a project, an idea you have, and have people from all areas involved to be able to discuss what will have an impact or not. (P2)
cod213	cat18	Meeting	Roadmap meetings are helping to increase alignment between BizDev teams	5	1	- "for the different teams to update each other in a more comprehensive forum involving all the people related to the product. So it was super important to give visibility to what was happening, and teams to get involved in the most relevant activities. Based on the principle that "I know what I should get involved in more than the other person knows what they should involve me in". (P13)
cod214	cat18	Meeting	Post-restructuring meetings focus on involving everyone, not just leaders	1	1	- "Also, no meeting exists with only the presence of the leaders. Everyone attends all meetings." (P8)
cod215	cat18; cat20; cat28	Context	The process reengineering project established a new development cycle consisting of goal setting, ideation, implementation, and reflection.	2	3	- "The idea was to create an ideation process around objectives. So, in summary, what we did was to declare a goal or result to be achieved within a period of time (...) We presented it to all the teams that worked on the app and collected feedback (...) Then the Design, Tech, Growth, and any area involved in Product development were invited to suggest possible solutions. (...) It was a moment of openness, we collected the ideas that the areas brought. We prioritized them according to the information we had." (P8)
cod216	cat18	Context	Reflection moment on deliveries and feedback collection after the execution of the development cycle.	1	1	- "We also collected feedback from the team about what they thought of this first phase and what was missing. We needed to improve the ideation part or how to better conduct certain stages. So there was a moment to review what this cycle was and see what improvements we could make for the next cycles, continuing to refine this system." (P8)
cod217	cat18	Perception	The process reengineering project was able to introduce new processes because the organizer was legitimized by the management.	2	1	- "The person needs to be legitimized. What happened with the Product Manager? He was legitimized by the CPO. The CPO said, "Guys, this guy is going to do the process. Listen to what he has to say"."
cod218	cat18	Context	Process reengineering project	29	1	- "So, every week, those responsible for the project would meet to discuss progress. And then at the end, there was a final delivery point (...) To see: "Did we achieve the result we wanted? Didn't we? What went wrong?". So that was the process we put in place for the first time a few months ago." (P8)
cod219	cat19	Responsibility	Product Manager with responsibility for finding and applying the best practices and processes for the teams' routine.	1	1	to find the best practices of day-to-day work of how we organize ourselves, whether we should have squads or not, what process we use to deliver, whether it's Scrum, Kanban, etc. It's very much the structural part of the work. (P8)
cod220	cat19	Responsibility	Product Manager with no management responsibility over the different BizDev areas	1	1	- "So I don't have management over Dev, Designers, people from the Growth team, Data, or any other team, but I have a primary responsibility in the day-to-day to connect these teams." (P8)

cod221	cat19	Responsibility	Product Manager responsible for ensuring touch points throughout the project to prevent deviations from the original strategy	1	1	- "So I have to ensure that these people are talking to each other, from the very beginning, throughout the project, and at the final delivery. That there are these touch points, so that information is not lost and we don't end up implementing something that doesn't make sense for the user, that is too difficult for the Tech team, or that the user acquisition team doesn't know about." (P8)
cod222	cat19	Responsibility	Product Manager responsible for guiding work and establishing a common focus for the areas	1	1	- "Facilitating communication on a day-to-day basis, helping to remove obstacles, guiding the work, and providing a focus so that the teams can connect." (P8)
cod223	cat19	Responsibility	Product Manager responsible for ensuring that the most suitable people for the project are participating in decision-making	1	1	- "The point of communication is to ensure that the information is reaching those who need it, and that the decision-maker, the person who is closest to the work, is making the decision." (P8)
cod224	cat20; cat26	Perception	Involving more areas in the decision-making process makes it slower, but more assertive.	2	2	- "TeamWork is great, but it slows down the delivery speed. So if you want to be fast, don't use agile methodology. Don't spend too much time discussing in a group. Make a decision, execute it, and do it. It will always be faster because there is less work to make the decision. If you want to increase the accuracy of things, then yes, the output will suffer because, again, it's a balance." (P8)
cod225	cat20	Tool	Use of Monday to track task progress	10	1	- "For issue tracking, it's Monday" (P8)
cod226	cat20	Tool	Use of Slack to centralize discussions	3	1	- "We use Slack in a group where everyone is there (...) So we always try to send a message that everyone can see, and if possible, tag the coordinator of each of these areas, and they delegate who will be responsible for resolving the issue for us." (P3)
cod227	cat20; cat28	Requirements	Use of a shared board containing the main product deliverables across teams	1	2	- "I think the team, from what I've seen in terms of usage, mostly uses a common board that shows the main project deliverables." (P8)
cod228	cat20	Perception	Retrospective meetings brought by the process reengineering project have increased transparency about events	1	1	Retrospective (meetings), which I think is the most important thing in Agile, the Product Manager also started doing, so all of these things to improve (communication) clarity. (P14)
cod229	cat20	Perception	Sharing progress and feature results democratizing the decision-making process	1	1	- "and then we track how the feature performed. This is all really important for democratization. So in this process I had much more involvement from the Content Coordinator, much more involvement from the Designer, and much more involvement from the developers themselves, who previously stayed behind the leadership and now are more involved in all of this." (P14)
cod230	cat20	Results	Process reengineering project democratizes and increases transparency of the decision-making process	6	1	- "This whole process is more about democratizing access and providing transparency, which are the principles of Agile methodology, which are communication and transparency, that's it." (P14)
cod231	cat20	Results	Process restructuring project avoiding decisions being made in silos	2	1	- "Well, it turned out that there weren't really any major app changes that people didn't understand. Because it's unlikely that this would happen, given that we have daily meetings that show our work. We communicate and share our work in Slack channels." (P8)
cod232	cat21; cat26	Prioritization	Development team prioritizing features independently of the Business team	5	2	Q: "Who notices the bugs and prioritizes them today?" A: "The team (of developers) itself does that." (P5)

cod233	cat21; cat25	Conflict	Conflict caused by development team not prioritizing technical debts	3	2	- "Overall, these (dashboards, metrics) were done by developers, and not people from the data team, and that can create a conflict, because people with data skills have better knowledge. (...) And this is a technical debt which, like all technical debts, is not very glamorous to be done and resolved." (P13)
cod234	cat21	Prioritization	Constant reprioritization of development tasks	3	1	- "So there's a priority involved in the to-do list. What often happens at CompanyP with high frequency is what we call "the bombs that arrive"." "So... (new) priorities come to CompanyP even with a high frequency." (P5)
cod235	cat21	Prioritization	Development leader participating more in prioritization discussions with the Business team than the rest of the team	2	1	- "Re-prioritization comes directly from the product team and usually goes to the mobile development coordinator." (P6)
cod236	cat21	Prioritization	Urgencies reprioritizing tasks, increasing their priority over other tasks	3	1	- "We use Crashlytics to measure app crashes, sometimes when something breaks, (...) we prioritize that." (P1)
cod237	cat21	Prioritization	Re-prioritization of features within a delivery to meet a deadline	2	1	- "There are things that have a hard deadline. (...) so if we don't make it, we take something out of feature T to not delay the fixed deadline. But this decision is made by the team (development) itself." (P1)
cod238	cat21	Prioritization	Tasks ordered by pre-defined priorities	5	1	- "We have a Trello with a backlog of all tasks that we take in order, they are sorted by a priority that we decide kind of informally." (P1)
cod239	cat21; cat25	Conflict	Business team not taking into consideration prioritizations proposed by technology teams	7	2	- "I said 'Dude, we have this thing here that is really important, and it's stagnating, you know.' And I don't exactly know why. If it's some kind of fear, if they're not giving as much priority to the project. (...) Now, if these things weren't done because of a product decision, weren't done because of a... I don't know, Growth decision. Or simply because they thought my idea was crap, I don't know." (P11)
cod240	cat21	Tool	Use of Trello to organize team tasks	10	1	- "We have a Trello with a backlog of all tasks that we take in order, they are sorted by a priority that we decide kind of informally." (P1)
cod241	cat21; cat22	Requirements	Development team using data and metrics to justify business decisions	10	2	- "If it's something that will have a direct impact on the user experience, then we have to justify it connecting the feature to some metrics. It can be engagement, it can be financial results. And we have to make the link between this functionality that we are doing and these metrics. When it's something more internal, like attacking technical debt, or making an operational improvement, then the data is more focused on team productivity, the number of tasks we can accomplish, how long it takes us to do each task, system availability, problem rate, user feedback as well." (P15)
cod242	cat21; cat28	Meeting	Feature prioritization meeting involving Business and Technology	5	2	- "We had meetings with the Product team where we defined priorities." (P11)
cod243	cat21; cat22	Tool	Use of Crashlytics to detect bugs	3	2	- "The team uses Crashlytics to measure the crashes of the app." (P1)
cod244	cat21	Prioritization	Development team prioritizing internal technology demands, such as optimizations, technical debts, and bugs.	4	1	- "So for example, on a point you raised about tech debt. It's something that technology needs to do, and that will have an impact on the Product side, probably not being released or not being done. So we always need to bring in these situations the 'why' we are being affected by those problems and how solving those problems will improve our productivity, or how it will allow us to develop the features that Product (team) wants us to do" (P15)

cod245	cat21	Prioritization	Feature prioritization based on technical difficulties	3	1	- "It's because the Android app is running on a version behind Unity compared to iOS, and migrating Android is more complicated, that's why they launched iOS first. But it was more of a technical issue than a business one." (P1)
cod246	cat21	Prioritization	Reprioritization proposed by the development team	1	1	Q: Who initiates the reprioritization? A: "Ourselves (mobile development team)" (P6)
cod247	cat22	Practice	Developers implementing/monitoring A/B tests to measure the results of a feature	3	1	- "I follow metrics on our platforms, I do A/B tests on Firebase" (P6) - "Whenever we add a usability feature or something related to that, we do A/B testing, and we do it ourselves on the technology team" (P1)
cod248	cat22	Practice	Development Analyst not used to extracting data/indicators	1	1	- "I don't usually take these metrics and expose them to the business team. But sometimes our coordinator does it." (P15)
cod249	cat22	Conflict	Development team working on data modeling/extraction without consulting with the BI - Business Intelligence team, acting incorrectly and hindering the work of business teams	5	1	- "To cite a specific point related to event analytics. In general, they were done by developers, and not from the data team, which can create conflicts because people who work with data have better knowledge. This is a sensitive issue that ends up impacting other areas." (P13)
cod250	cat22	Conflict	Business team having less trust in the technology team due to features with problems and data modeling that makes analysis difficult.	1	1	- "So maybe there's a drop in Business's trust in technology. Because they can't extract the results from the proposals they have." (P15)
cod251	cat22	Context	Most of the data/indicators extraction is done by the data team	1	1	- "But the major business indicators are usually extracted by the Data team." (P15)
cod252	cat22	Context	Product and Development teams seeking the Business Intelligence (BI) team for data analysis	7	1	- "We also started to work closely with BI, we use them more for their Know-How because we started to have an internal practice of doing these studies ourselves." (P5)
cod253	cat22	Tool	Use of Periscope to concentrate analysis over results indicators	1	1	It seems that the BI team will improve that. They create dashboards on Periscope, and we can follow along. (P4)
cod254	cat22; cat25	Context	Technology area tends to trust only decisions based/proven on quantitative data	4	2	- "I usually understand, especially because they usually bring data. And I feel like they are increasingly bringing data to support those ideas and proposals they make. So, especially when they bring that data, the level of confidence in those proposals increases." (P15)
cod255	cat22	Context	Use of indicators and metrics to determine success of features/projects	8	1	- "For each iteration we did, I built presentations showing both the KPIs we were impacting, the opportunities we had on the table, and what would be the next iterations for us to monitor these results even more." (P10)
cod256	cat22	Practice	Developers constantly extracting and monitoring business indicators.	12	1	- "Ssince it's a simpler analytics, we extract it ourselves. We took some numbers and saw that in the A/B testing scenario where the feature was present, on average, people consumed less content." (P1)
cod257	cat22	Practice	Technology team analyzing competitors	8	1	- "So we showed all the numbers, we took data from our competitors using AppAnnie and showed: 'look, this is our retention rate, compared to the retention rate of these apps (competitors) (...) And their retention rate is much higher than ours, you know'. So if we could take some of these features and bring them into our app, there's a chance we could increase our retention rate too." (P5)
cod258	cat23; cat26	Conflict	Projects proposed by technology having to succeed in a short time to continue receiving investment from the business area	3	2	- "(Making a critique of the current context) "And if it doesn't work in 20 days, I'll take away your resources and it's your fault for not proving yourself." That doesn't exist, no company can grow that way." (P14)

cod259	cat23	Requirements	Larger features being proposed by the business team	3	1	- "Our backlog is 70% bugfix and improvements that we ourselves identify. Larger features usually come from the product team." (P1)
cod260	cat23	Requirements	Development team defining feature requirements based on deadline given by the business team	3	1	- "We had an idea of what we wanted, but it was the product team who set the deadline, saying for example: 'We want it to be delivered in a month and a half or so'. So in a way, the requirements were guided by the product team's demands and when they wanted it delivered." (P9)
cod261	cat23	Requirements	Creation of a presentation to structure and detail requirements.	2	1	- "We had a presentation where we put everything together, and then we polished it. I think that was more it. We didn't structure anything beyond that." (P1)
cod262	cat23; cat26	Requirements	Development team defining MVP for a feature ideated by technology	2	2	- "So we had a presentation, and we were kind of just throwing everything in there, and then polishing it later. I think it was more like that. Like we didn't structure anything beyond that. And then we had to choose: 'Okay, this is what we wanted to deliver. We don't think we'll have time to deliver everything. We think we'll have time to deliver this minus these features. (...) But we try to aim for the smaller one, which is the minimum, the MVP. This we can deliver.'" (P9)
cod263	cat23	Requirements	Brainstorming done by the Development team to come up with new features or directions	4	1	- "We wanted to develop different features, we brainstormed, evaluated what was most important to us, which was retention, so we saw which features gave us more retention, we reached the feature T and structured this idea." (P1)
cod264	cat23; cat26	Requirements	Development team having autonomy to remove features from a delivery	4	2	Q: Does the decision to reduce scope stay only within the dev team? A: "Usually it stays only within the team. Yes, hardly ever do we escalate." (P5)
cod265	cat23	Context	Extensive work by a Technology member to showcase/sell the opportunity to work on their proposed direction	3	1	- "I decided to do it in parts. That is, I took my first pitch, showed it to my peers, my peers brought up questions, inputs, I improved the presentation, introduced more data, and then I presented it to other peers, then to superiors, then to the superior of the superior (...) until I reached the CEO." (P10)
cod266	cat23	Context	More senior members of Technology/Design are able to bring more insights/directions in terms of business	3	1	- "The coordinators, or specialists, the more senior people, they can bring insights on average, at least in relation to the feature, looking more at the business, not necessarily just thinking about the technical solution." (P13)
cod267	cat23	Context	Technology team impacting Business through cost reduction projects	1	1	- "We see the technology area impacting the business, for example with cost reduction projects, and I've seen this happen several times over the years, effectively increasing the product margin and making it more viable." (P10)
cod268	cat23	Requirements	Development team proposing feature focused on optimizing/automating recurring demands from the Business team	3	1	- "this integration and the idea of the benefits solution came from the team itself, it wasn't something that was idealized by Product. (...) So it was a solution that was initially created for a partner, but ended up becoming a business model that is now serving several partners." (P15)
cod269	cat23	Requirements	Development team proposing/defining features/directions	24	1	- "we already have examples of ideas that originate in programming or design and end up becoming something real and spreading again within the teams to be done" (P5)
cod270	cat24; cat26	Results	Feature proposed by Technology was successfully delivered.	8	2	- "there was, I think, this feature that came out of the technology area, and that was also discussed with several people from technology, especially from the Mobile team. They validated that idea, implemented it, and the results were very good. And now it's even becoming a successful case to be presented in various places." (P15) - "We did it. We did it." (P9)

cod271	cat24	Perception	Features proposed by technology may have been interrupted/abandoned too early without further attempts to evolve	3	1	- "But these are things that I think could have made a difference for us, at least to know that we invested enough time, tried enough before we gave up, or you know, to have a more formed view of what happened and if there are more possibilities to be explored." (P14)
cod272	cat24; cat26	Results	Feature proposed by technology did not achieve expected success because it did not involve other areas	6	2	- "Far from the acquisition and branding team that should promote or better understand his business model. So there were several decisions there that did not involve the teams that have more expertise and could add more. (...) So the feature's main premise is not so problematic, but the fact that its execution did not involve those stakeholders, in the case of the project, greatly affected the result it generated." (P8)
cod273	cat24	Results	Most of the features proposed by technology did not have the expected result	2	1	- "Unfortunately, most of them didn't. I think this is actually the norm. The norm is to try very hard, through good assumptions, good hypotheses, and not always having good results" (P10)
cod274	cat24; cat25; cat26	Results	Feature proposed by technology did not achieve expected success because it did not obtain political strength, because it did not convince/engage business management/directors.	3	3	- "it (featureT) was not worked on enough for us to make the decision if it was successful or not. So for me, what made it go wrong is not having enough political strength to continue. And that didn't happen because the Product Manager wasn't involved from the beginning, wasn't fully committed, didn't convince the CPO from the beginning. We had to make more noise to convince both of them. It had to be worked more with them that it was a killer asset." (P14)
cod275	cat24	Results	Feature proposed by technology leading to the creation of a new business unit in the company.	2	1	- "And this served as an eye-opener for an area that could be explored for another age group, which was not necessarily the age group that we target in ProductP." (P10)
cod276	cat24	Results	Feature proposed by the design team was not successful.	1	1	- "FeatureH came more from the Design team than from Product. It didn't work out, we're going to remove it." (P1)
cod277	cat25	Conflict	Lack of trust from technology teams about decisions made by other areas.	5	1	- "But usually when these decisions are made, I don't feel much confidence in what Product wants. And usually, Product has the final say." (P15)
cod278	cat25	Conflict	Prioritization conflicts causing features divided into stages to have parts of the delivery indefinitely postponed.	2	1	- "It's because of the process, which is how we prioritize features (...) And then I suggested something that was a little bit (...) It was a slightly bigger projec (...). It took a lot longer to implement because we had some issues (...) And then time passed, and now we're in a different moment, and this second part isn't going to be implemented, at least not in this first moment. And we don't know when it will be or how it will be." (P2)
cod279	cat25	Conflict	Conflict caused by Development team questioning decisions made by Business team	2	1	- "It was almost a month of Developers asking me how I was going to prove that a piece of content was appropriate using data. And it was something (...) that we shouldn't waste time on because it's already been proven, so it doesn't make sense for us to discuss it again. Otherwise, we'll end up discussing all the data from why gravity is gravity until we get back to programming code again." (P7)
cod280	cat25	Conflict	Difficulty in convincing Business team of the importance of working on technical debts	1	1	- "So for example, on a point you raised about tech debt. It's something that technology needs to do, and that will have an impact on the Product side, probably not being released or not being done. So we always need to bring in these situations the 'why' we are being affected by those problems and how solving those problems will improve our productivity, or how it will allow us to develop the features that Product (team) wants us to do" (P15)

cod281	cat25	Conflict	Business and Development teams disagreeing on what is best for the product.	1	1	- "So when you have this kind of discussion, this is a type of conflict that appears. Because one side says: 'we can only do it (...) in the best way if we have all this information from the user' and on the other hand, they want to remove as much friction as possible from the path so that the customer can already see the value of our product. I think this is a point of conflict." (P15)
cod282	cat25	Conflict	Business team not taking into consideration the opinion of technology and making decisions that prioritize financial gains over customer experience and future product maintenance.	3	1	- "I feel that in many moments, several Product decisions are made with a focus on financial results. So these financial results end up overriding customer needs, or some user experiences, or other functionalities that would be much more interesting for the user." (P15)
cod283	cat26	Perception	Perception that processes are necessary to regulate the idealization of the heroic worker	1	1	- "But when you take CompanyA for example, why does the hero feeling work there? Because they have so much process that is clear to you, besides having the process and being well evaluated, I need to be the hero and work 30 hours a day. But I'll get overtime pay, and my financial return will be exponential. So, I think they took a bit of this thing from CompanyA, threw it into CompanyP, and mixed it up and that became this." (P14)
cod284	cat26	Culture	Company culture encourages projects for the company to be worked on in parallel, outside of work hours	6	1	- "This (working on new projects in overtime) is encouraged. If we say that this is not encouraged, it is a lie. A lot of cool things come out of it. And there are people who don't care, there are people who like it. Man, CompanyP is the place for you." (P14)
cod285	cat26; cat27	Context	Two parallel decision tracks between the Business (Product) and Technology (Development and Design) areas	2	2	- "What I felt when I joined ProductP: The product team was very isolated, very close to the CPO, maybe close to the board of directors, and the technical team was closer to the Head of Technology, closer to his influence, and making decisions somewhat without consulting the product team. So you had 2 parallel tracks of decision" (P14)
cod286	cat27	Conflict	Product Analyst feels a lack of clarity/transparency about how business decisions are made	8	1	- "All of this is important to us. But I don't know, I can't tell you if it came or not because both decision-making processes were not clear. At least I didn't participate in the process" (P14)
cod287	cat27	Perception	Product Analyst perceives that the business area should have to convince other areas more about its directions	1	1	- "They (high management) are making the decision about what we are going to put in the product. And we need to sell them on the fact that it makes sense. I think it should be the opposite. They should be selling us" (P14)
cod288	cat27	Perception	Before the reengineering project, requirements were defined in a non organized way, by different areas	1	1	- "From what I understood, from what I had perceived, it was more or less like this. We had a demand that came without much organization, so it could come from anywhere" (P14)
cod289	cat27	Meeting	LiveOps meeting for leaders to present projects	1	1	- "It will be periodic, every... I think every 15 days, only with the leaders. And then the leaders will bring some points, about projects, possible projects" (P12)
cod290	cat27	Meeting	Meeting to present strategy being only expository, without space for discussion.	1	1	- "There is a meeting where the product director makes the decision. (...) I can't contest him (...) It's impractical. So these forums are not there to provide transparency in that way" (P14)
cod291	cat27	Context	Centralization of decision-making power in the heads of the departments	2	1	- "I think today it's a little more centralized in the Heads (eg: Head of Technology) and the Heads are passing it on to the teams, kind of cascading. I think this is a bit bad because it ends up lengthening the time" (P2)

cod292	cat27	Conflict	Decision-making being driven by politics: whoever imposes themselves in communication, who has more influence and charisma	7	1	- "I really think that CompanyP really needed these processes because prioritization, decision-making, it's extremely subjective. (...) This is terrible because it leads to this issue of charisma, the most charismatic person, who speaks the loudest, who positions themselves better, is the one who makes the decision, and that's very bad" (P14)
cod293	cat28	Requirements	Development and Content teams seeking a middle ground solution that meets the demand and is easy to develop	1	1	- "It happens quite often, we always try to find a middle ground in something that is simple for us to use in the content area and that is simple to develop. We always look for an interesting middle ground for both parties. It's not usually difficult to find this middle ground." (P3)